

Prolonged Self-healing of Laminated Composites via *In Situ* Thermal Remending

Alexander D. Snyder¹, Z. Phillips², J. Turicek¹, Prof. Patrick^{1,2}

¹ Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering

² Department of Civil, Construction, and Environmental Engineering
North Carolina State University (NCSU)

Outline

- Background/Motivation
- Constituent materials, System architecture, and Composite fabrication
- Mechanical Testing and Evaluation:
 - (I) in-plane tension
 - (II) mode-I fracture
- *In Situ* Self-Healing Results
- Investigation of Underlying Healing Mechanisms
- Summary/Conclusions

Motivation

- Fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites ubiquitous in modern engineered structures:
(1) high specific strength/stiffness, (2) corrosion resistance, (3) geometric/constituent versatility

Aerospace

Automotive

Naval

Energy

Civil

Woven FRP Composites

- Hierarchical materials with structural advantage, but also inherent susceptibility to damage

Laminated Woven Composite

ASM International (2010)

Interlaminar Delamination

Polymer 53 (2012)

Self-healing Background

- Delamination detection is difficult and manual repairs are costly – self-healing offers a bioinspired solution

Repairs costly/time consuming

www.dsto.defence.gov.au

Possible catastrophic failure

USAF Hilltop Times

Self-healing Strategies

Capsule-based

Vascular

Intrinsic

Nature 409 (2001)

Adv. Mater. 22 (2010)

Nature 540 (2016)

Limitations:

- Single-heal
- Mixing difficult
- Small-scale repair
- Blockages

Advantages:

- Multiple-heals
- No external agent

Soft Materials

Angew. Chem. 51 (2012)

- Interface contact
- Room-temperature repair

Structural Materials

Science 295 (2002)

- Elevated temperature repair

Thermal Remending

- Inclusion of thermoplastic phase + heat provides capacity for structural composite repair
- Poly(ethylene-co-methacrylic acid) – EMAA – is a commodity polymer with proven self-healing ability

Self-healing achieved *ex situ* and/or above glass-transition temperature (T_g)

Thermoplastic-modified Matrices

Polymer **92** (2016)

Particles and Interwoven Fibers

Interlayer Integration

Macromol. Mater. Eng. **295** (2010)

ACS Appl. Mater. Inter. **1** (2009)

Compos. Part A **43** (2012)

Compos. Part A **43** (2012)

New Approach: *In Situ* Thermal Remending

- Self-healing below laminate glass-transition temperature (T_g) via *in situ* heating

3D-printing onto preform substrate

Pristine multifunctional composite laminate

Internal delamination damage

Self-healing via *in situ* thermal remending

Textile Resistive Heaters

Conductive Carbon Whiskers

Laminate Integration

Virgin EMAA Pellets

In-house Filament

3D Printing EMAA

Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM)

Preform Patterning and Laminate Fabrication

- FDM to micro-pattern EMAA in serpentine geometry directly onto woven reinforcement = scalability

GFRP layup (16 plies):
 $[0/90]_2/RH/0/90/0/EMAA$
 $/90/0/90/RH/[0/90]_2$

CFRP layup (8 plies):
 $0/90/RH/0/EMAA/90/RH/0/90$

Post-cure: 2h @ 121°C + 2h @ 150°C

X-ray Computed Tomography Reconstruction

Structural Integrity: In-Plane Tension

- Investigate effect of composite modification(s) on in-plane tensile performance[†]

Digital Image Correlation (DIC)

$n = 3$

9

[†] ASTM D-3039

Thermo-mechanical Characterization

- Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) to determine thermal remodeling below T_g and retain in-service structural performance

DMA Fixture & Specimen

3-pt Flexure (1Hz, 5°C/min)[†]

$$E^* = E' + iE'' \quad \tan(\delta) = \frac{E''}{E'}$$

Fiber-Composite Constituents:

Matrix: DGEBA epoxy system

Reinforcement: Glass (GFRP) and Carbon Fiber (CFRP); $V_f = 0.51$ [‡]

Elastic (storage) Modulus Comparison

	E' 23°C, GPa	E' T_g , GPa	E' 130°C, GPa
Epoxy	2.9	0.1 (3%)	1.3 (45%)
GFRP	16.7	8.7 (52%)	14.2 (85%)
CFRP	25.7	13.5 (53%)	22.5 (88%)

*Percentages (%) represent retained E' vs. value at RT = 23°C

Resistive Heater Calibration

[†] ASTM E-1640

[‡] ASTM D-2584

Mechanical Evaluation: Mode I Fracture

- Double Cantilever Beam* (DCB) for self-healing assays

$$\dagger G_I = \frac{1}{b} \frac{\Delta U}{\Delta a}$$

$$\Delta U = \int_0^{\delta} P d\hat{\delta} \Big|_{\Delta a}$$

$$\ddagger \hat{\eta} := \frac{G_{IC}^{healed}}{G_{IC}^{virgin}} \times 100$$

In Situ Heating

Heal Cycle: (heat) 15 min. @ 130°C
(cool) 30 min. until RT

Experimental Transient Response

*ASTM D-5528

†J. Mater. Sci. Lett. **8** (1989)

‡Adv. Mater. **26** (2014)

Virgin Fracture and *In Situ* Self-Healing Behavior

- Virgin fracture resistance & healing efficiency scale w/ EMAA areal coverage

3D Printed Pattern

Fracture direction

8H Satin Weave

Topological Investigation of Healing Performance

- Fiber-reinforcement type influences self-healing behavior

Virgin Cycle (V)

*scale bars = 50 μm

Heal Cycle 5 (H5)

Heal Cycle 10 (H10)

Heal Cycle 20 (H20)

Capacity for Sustained Self-healing

- 100 heal cycles achieved in GFRP (and CFRP) w/o significant degradation in recovery

*Nat. Comm. 13 (2022)

*scale bars = 25 μm

Eventual collapse of microporous network by heal cycle 40

FTIR Spectroscopy Reveals Chemical Mechanisms

- ATR-FTIR spectroscopy of EMAA supports propensity for perpetual healing

Key Chemical Reactions[†]

TYPE I - Oxirane/Carboxylic Acid

TYPE II – Amine/Carboxylic Acid

[†]Vib. Spectrosc. **52** (2010)

FTIR Spectroscopy of EMAA

Invariant: 719 cm^{-1} Methylene rocking

Reactive: 1406 cm^{-1} Carboxylic Acid Hydroxyl stretch, 1535 cm^{-1} Carboxylic Acid Ammonium Salt stretch, 1710 cm^{-1} Ester Carbonyl stretch, 3247 cm^{-1} Hydroxyl stretch

FTIR Spectral Evolution of EMAA

Summary/Conclusions

- Achieved ***in situ self-healing*** via thermal remending in fiber-composites below the ***glass-transition temperature*** (T_g).
- ***3D printed EMAA*** patterns have ***negligible impact*** on in-plane ***structural integrity*** and ***increase mode-I fracture resistance*** (G_{IC}). Textile ***resistive heaters*** have ***minor impact*** on GFRP properties.
- ***Increasing*** EMAA areal ***coverage increases*** virgin ***fracture resistance*** and ***healing efficiency*** ($> 100\%$).
- ***Superior*** healing performance in ***GFRP*** vs. CFRP due to physical properties of ***fabric architecture*** and ***surface chemistry*** that promotes ***EMAA microporous network*** and ***crack tortuosity***.
- ***Rapid*** sub-hour (45 min.) and ***extended*** ***in situ*** heal cycles (100+) demonstrates propensity for ***practical*** and ***perpetual*** in-service repair.

Snyder *et. al*, Prolonged In situ Self-healing in Structural Composites via Thermo-reversible Entanglement, *Nat. Comm.* **13** (2022).

U.S. Patent No. 16/944,675 (Issued March 2023)

Acknowledgements

Funding Source:

US Army Corps of Engineers
Strategic Environmental Research and Defense Program (SERDP)
Weapons Systems and Platforms (WP)
Grant # W912HQ21C0044

US Air Force Office of Scientific Research
Young Investigator Program (YIP)
Grant # FA9550-18-1-0048

US Army Corps
of Engineers®

Academic Collaborators:

Prof. Patrick

Zach

Sandeep

Jack

C. Diesendruck

K. Nakshatrala

